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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
CED	Centre for Demographic Studies
INE	National Statistics Institute
EUROSTAT	Statistical Office of the European Union
UUNN	United Nations
ESP	Spain
ACs	Autonomous Communities

SUMMARY

This document describes the multiregional model implemented for the realization of medium and long term demographic scenarios for Spain and the Autonomous Communities. The model provides a set of inputs that are subsequently used in the SPANDAM simulation model, such as mortality and fertility rates and migration patterns according to different scenarios of demographic evolution of the Spanish population. On the other hand, the numerical results of the projection of the Autonomous Communities also provide a general reference framework for the future evolution of the population that allows the results to be contrasted with those obtained for the area under study in the SPANDAM simulation model.

The document is structured in three sections. The first describes the general projection model used and the different calculation algorithms implemented to make the projection for Spain and the Autonomous Communities. The second explains the different hypotheses formulated on the future evolution of demographic phenomena, as well as the methodologies used for their projection. Finally, the third section presents some graphs and tables that summarize the main results of the three demographic scenarios constructed for Spain and the Autonomous Communities in the medium and long term.

PROJECTION MODEL AND CALCULATION ALGORITHMS

The projection was made using the components method, which is based on the classic compensating equation that explains the growth or decline of a population over a period as a function of the demographic phenomena that determine its evolution. The approach of the method is generational, since it projects the future evolution of the population of the different cohorts. For those cohorts that are present at the initial moment of the projection, those who die or emigrate are subtracted and those who immigrate during the projection period are added. At the same time, births occurring during the years being projected are estimated, and we proceed in the same way, subtracting those who die or emigrate and adding those who emigrate. In the model, deaths, births and emigrants depend on the population and, therefore, are estimated from rates applied to the population of the cohorts, while immigrants are considered as absolute values to be added to the population of the different cohorts.

The projection model approach is a multi-regional one, as it is the most suitable for projecting different territorial levels (Willekens, 1984, 1990; INE 2022). The advantages of this approach are: a) it guarantees the consistency of the results of the population and demographic phenomena, both in terms of the demographic equation and between the different territorial levels; b) it facilitates the formulation of the hypotheses, since they are formulated for Spain and transferred to the Autonomous Communities by methods that take into account territorial differences; c) immigration and emigration are treated separately; and d) the results are disaggregated by sex and simple age for both population and demographic phenomena.

1.1. NOMENCLATURE

Numbers		Rates	
P	population		
N	births	f	fertility
D	deaths	m	mortality
I	foreign immigrants		
Iint	internal migrants		
E	foreign emigrants	e	foreign emigration
Eint	internal migrants	eint	internal migration

Variables	Subindexes and values	
Year	t	
Territory	ESP	Spain
	ACs	Autonomous Communities
Sex	s	
	m	man
	f	women
Age	x	
		simple age 0 to 100+
		Starting population up to 100+
		Results 99+ (effective events)
		100+ (effective populations)

Birth cohort	c n corresponds to births, is the corresponding year in each projection year.
Origin of immigration	Abroad: with foreign countries Interior: between ACs
Destination of emigrations	Abroad: with foreign countries Interior: between ACs

Time reference of data

Population data refer to January 1 of each year, while demographic phenomena cover the entire year, from January 1 to December 31 of each year.

Triangularization

As a general nomenclature, the year-age dimension rate is defined with a single letter and the corresponding year-cohort dimension rate is defined by doubling the letter. For example, m_x is the year-age mortality rate and mm_x is the year-cohort rate.

1.2. AUXILIARY FORMULA: TRIANGULARIZATION

The central calculation routines of the projection system require the introduction of the inputs from a cohort-period perspective (i.e., generational rates for each year of the projection), while the hypotheses are formulated from an age-period perspective (i.e., squared rates in terms of a Lexis Diagram). This difference requires a prior transformation process of the inputs of the different demographic phenomena, which is called triangularization.

Triangularization of annual projection inputs

There are three different formulas depending on the event in question, and they change according to age:

1) Fertility

$x = 14, s = f$	$ff_{s,14}^t = \frac{f_{s,15}^t}{2}$
$x = 15, 16, \dots, 48, s = f$	$ff_{s,x}^t = \frac{f_{s,x}^t + f_{s,x+1}^t}{2}$
$x = 49, s = f$	$ff_{s,49}^t = \frac{f_{s,49}^t}{2}$

2) Immigration

$c = n$	$II_{s,n}^t = \frac{I_{s,0}^t}{2}$
$c = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 98$	$II_{s,c}^t = \frac{I_{s,x}^t + I_{s,x+1}^t}{2}$
$c = 99+$	$II_{99+}^t = \frac{I_{s,99}^t}{2} + I_{s,100+}^t$

3) Mortality and emigration (external and internal)

$c = n$	$tt_{s,n}^t = \frac{t_{s,0}^t}{2}$
$c = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 99+$	$tt_{s,c}^t = \frac{t_{s,x}^t + t_{s,x+1}^t}{2}$

1.3. INPUTS FROM MODEL

Starting population	$P_{T,s,x}^{t_0}$	ESP, ACs	$x = 0, 1, \dots, 99, 100+$
Mortality	$mm_{T,s,x}^t$	ESP, ACs	$x = n, 0, 1, \dots, 98, 99+$
Fertility	$ff_{T,d,x}^t$	ESP, ACs	$x = 14, 15, \dots, 49$
Foreign emigration	$ee_{T,s,x}^t$	ESP, ACs	$x = n, 0, 1, \dots, 98, 99+$
Domestic emigration	$eeint_{proc,s,x}^{t,proc,dest}$	ACs	$x = n, 0, 1, \dots, 98, 99+$
Foreign immigration	$II_{T,s,x}^t$	ESP, ACs	$x = n, 0, 1, \dots, 98, 99+$
Domestic immigration	$II_{dest,s,x}^{RESP,t}$	ACs	$x = n, 0, 1, \dots, 98, 99+$

Note on internal emigration

Internal emigration, between the ACs, is treated in the multiregional projection model based on emigration rates by sex, simple age, AC of origin and destination AC.

The hypotheses are formulated on an emigration rate by sex and simple age for the Autonomous Communities of origin and on an origin-destination distribution matrix by sex and simple age of this migration. From these two inputs the model calculates the emigration rates required by the model as follows:

$$\{eeint_{T,s,x}^{t,T,dest} = eeint_{T,s,x}^t * M_{T,s,x}^{t,T,dest}\}$$

Where T is the AC for which the internal migration rates are estimated, and {dest} are the remaining ACs.

Note on internal emigration

The internal immigration of each Autonomous Community is the sum of immigrants from the rest of Spain.

1.4. CENTRAL FORMULAS

1.4.1. CALCULATION OF BIRTHS

To calculate births, the year-cohort fertility rates are applied to the female population of childbearing age. The calculation formulas are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x = 15 \quad N_{T,d,15}^t &= \left(\frac{P_{T,d,14}^t + P_{T,d,15}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * ff_{T,d,14}^t + \left(\frac{P_{T,d,15}^t + P_{T,d,16}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{ff_{T,d,15}^t}{2} \\
 x = 16-48 \quad N_{T,d,x}^t &= \left(\frac{P_{T,d,x-1}^t + P_{T,d,x}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{ff_{T,d,x-1}^t}{2} + \left(\frac{P_{T,d,x}^t + P_{T,d,x+1}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{ff_{T,d,x}^t}{2} \\
 x = 49 \quad N_{T,d,49}^t &= \left(\frac{P_{T,d,48}^t + P_{T,d,49}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{ff_{T,d,48}^t}{2} + \left(\frac{P_{T,d,49}^t + P_{T,d,50}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * ff_{T,d,49}^t
 \end{aligned}$$

Finally, births are totalled by mother's age and distributed by sex based on a Birth Masculinity Index (IMN, currently 0.5168).

$$N_{T,m}^t = IMN * \sum_{x=15}^{49} N_{T,d,x}^t \quad N_{T,f}^t = (1 - IMN) * \sum_{x=15}^{49} N_{T,d,x}^t$$

1.4.2. CALCULATION OF THE POPULATION N

Population aged 0 years, Spain

$$P_{ESP,s,0}^{t+1} = \frac{[1 - 0,5 * (mm_{ESP,s,n}^t + ee_{ESP,s,n}^t)] * N_{ESP,s}^t + II_{ESP,s,n}^t}{[1 + 0,5 * (mm_{ESP,s,n}^t + ee_{ESP,s,n}^t)]}$$

Population aged 0 years, ACs (T= ACs)

$$P_{T,s,0}^{t+1} = \frac{[1 - 0,5 * (mm_{T,s,n}^t + ee_{T,s,n}^t + \sum_{dest \neq T} eint_{T,s,n}^{t,T,dest})] * N_{T,s}^t + II_{T,s,n}^t + \sum_{proc \neq T} eint_{proc,s,n}^{t,proc,T} * N_{proc,s}^t}{[1 + 0,5 * (mm_{T,s,n}^t + ee_{T,s,n}^t + \sum_{dest \neq T} eint_{T,s,n}^{t,T,dest})]}$$

Population aged 1-99 years, Spain

$$P_{ESP,s,x+1}^{t+1} = \frac{[1 - 0,5 * (mm_{ESP,s,x}^t + ee_{ESP,s,x}^t)] * P_{ESP,s,x}^t + II_{ESP,s,x}^t}{[1 + 0,5 * (mm_{ESP,s,x}^t + ee_{ESP,s,x}^t)]}$$

Population aged 1-99 years, ACs (T= ACs)

$$P_{T,s,x+1}^{t+1} = \frac{[1 - 0,5 * (mm_{T,s,x}^t + ee_{T,s,x}^t + \sum_{dest \neq T} eint_{T,s,x}^{t,T,dest})] * P_{T,s,x}^t + II_{T,s,x}^t + \sum_{proc \neq T} eint_{proc,s,x}^{t,proc,T} * P_{proc,s,x}^t}{[1 + 0,5 * (mm_{T,s,x}^t + ee_{T,s,x}^t + \sum_{dest \neq T} eint_{T,s,x}^{t,T,dest})]}$$

Open group population, Spain

$$P_{ESP,s,100+}^{t+1} = \frac{[1 - 0,5 * (mm_{ESP,s,99+}^t + ee_{ESP,s,99+}^t)] * (P_{ESP,s,99}^t + P_{ESP,s,100+}^t) + II_{ESP,s,99+}^t}{[1 + 0,5 * (mm_{ESP,s,99+}^t + ee_{ESP,s,99+}^t)]}$$

Open group population, ACs (T= ACs)

$$P_{T,s,100+}^{t+1} = \frac{[1 - 0,5 * (mm_{T,s,99+}^t + ee_{T,s,99+}^t + \sum_{dest \neq T} eint_{T,s,99+}^{t,T,dest})] * (P_{T,s,99}^t + P_{T,s,100+}^t) + II_{T,s,99+}^t}{[1 + 0,5 * (mm_{T,s,99+}^t + ee_{T,s,99+}^t + \sum_{dest \neq T} eint_{T,s,99+}^{t,T,dest})]} + \frac{\sum_{proc \neq T} eint_{proc,s,99+}^{t,proc,T} * (P_{proc,s,99}^t + P_{proc,s,100+}^t)}{[1 + 0,5 * (mm_{T,s,99+}^t + ee_{T,s,99+}^t + \sum_{dest \neq T} eint_{T,s,99+}^{t,T,dest})]}$$

1.4.3. CALCULATION OF DEMOGRAPHIC EVENTS

In the projection model, deaths and emigrants are obtained by cohort-period, which requires a subsequent transformation to obtain them classified by age and year of projection. This transformation is carried out using the formulas:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x = 0 \quad R_{T,s,0}^t &= \left(\frac{N_{T,s}^t + P_{T,s,0}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * tt_{T,s,n}^t + \left(\frac{P_{T,s,0}^t + P_{T,s,1}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{tt_{T,s,0}^t}{2} \\
 x = 1-98 \quad R_{T,s,x}^t &= \left(\frac{P_{T,s,x-1}^t + P_{T,s,x}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{tt_{T,s,x-1}^t}{2} + \left(\frac{P_{T,s,x}^t + P_{T,s,x+1}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{tt_{T,s,x}^t}{2} \\
 x = 99+ \quad R_{T,s,99+}^t &= \left(\frac{P_{T,s,98}^t + P_{T,s,99}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * \frac{tt_{T,s,98}^t}{2} + \left(\frac{P_{T,s,99}^t + P_{T,s,100+}^t + P_{T,s,100+}^{t+1}}{2} \right) * tt_{T,s,99+}^t
 \end{aligned}$$

with: tt	R
mm	D
ee	E
eint ^{proc,dest}	Eint ^{proc,dest}

For emigrants and internal immigrants, they will be calculated:

$$Eint_{T,s,x}^t = \sum_{dest \neq T} Eint_{T,s,x}^{t,T,dest} \quad i \quad Iint_{T,s,x}^t = \sum_{proc \neq T} Eint_{proc,s,x}^{t,proc,T}$$

For foreign immigrants, no transformation is necessary, since the hypotheses are formulated from the age-period perspective and therefore this information is directly available.

1.5. AUXILIARY FORMULA: TERRITORIAL ADJUSTMENT

The results of the projection, both in terms of population and events, of the lower territorial areas, in this case the Autonomous Regions, must be consistent with the results obtained in the projection of the corresponding higher area, Spain.

To achieve this consistency, the model proposes an iterative procedure that adjusts the inputs of the different units projected at the territorial level until the sum of the projection of these units is identical to the previous projection of the higher level. This adjustment process is only necessary for demographic phenomena that are projected from rates and that are related to the higher level: i.e., mortality, fertility and foreign emigration. In contrast, this adjustment is not necessary in the case of immigration, since it is based on absolute values and distribution matrices, nor in the case of internal migration, since it does not have an impact on the results of the higher level.

The procedure consists of an iterative algorithm in which the rates for the projection of the lower scopes are adjusted by a factor calculated by comparing the estimate of the upper scope and the results of the sum of the estimate of the lower scopes. Operationally, a series of auxiliary projections are made for the lower domains with scaled adjustments, so that the sum of their projected events is identical to that previously obtained in the projection of the upper domain.

Algorithm

Are lower scopes that cover the entire territory of a given higher scope: $\{ambI\} \equiv ambS$

1) $i=0$ ('i' indicates the order of iteration) We start from the data of the projection of the upper region: $t_{s,c}^{ambS,t}$ and the projection of the corresponding lower regions with their projection inputs is performed:

$$t_{s,c}^{ambI,t} \left(\equiv \hat{t}(0)_{s,c}^{ambI,t} \right) \text{ with results } P(i)_{s,c}^{ambI,t}$$

2) With the results of the projection and the inputs from the lower regions, a value for the whole upper region is estimated by means of:

$$\hat{t}(i)_{s,c}^{ambS,t} = \frac{\sum_{ambI} \left(\hat{t}(i)_{s,c}^{ambI,t} \cdot P(i)_{s,c}^{ambI,t} \right)}{\sum_{ambI} P(i)_{s,c}^{ambI,t}}$$

3) A comparison factor is calculated:

$$f(i)_{s,c}^{ambI,t} = \frac{t_{s,c}^{ambS,t}}{\hat{t}(i)_{s,c}^{ambS,t}}$$

4) $i=i+1$, this factor is applied to the inputs of the lower regions:

$$\hat{t}(i+1)_{s,c}^{ambI,t} = f(i)_{s,c}^{ambI,t} \cdot \hat{t}(i)_{s,c}^{ambI,t}$$

5) With the new inputs $\hat{t}(i+1)_{s,c}^{ambI,t}$ a new projection is made.

6) Repeat (2) to (5) until the outputs of the projection of the lower regions remain unchanged and the comparison with the results of the projection of the upper region is consistent, i.e:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} S(i)_{s,c}^{ambI,t} \equiv S(i+1)_{s,c}^{ambI,t} \equiv S_{s,c}^{ambI,t} \quad \forall s,c \\ i \\ \sum_{ambI} S^{ambI,t} \equiv S^{ambS,t} \end{array} \right.$$

These are the definitive projection outputs for the ranges $\{ambI\}$

HYPOTHESIS

With regard to the future evolution of the demographic components, three hypotheses have been drawn up for the future evolution of mortality, fertility and foreign migration for Spain as a whole and its Autonomous Communities at the 2099 horizon. For the Autonomous Communities, a single hypothesis on the future evolution of the intensity of migratory flows between these regions has also been drawn up. The combination of the low hypotheses of the different demographic phenomena configures the low scenario of future demographic evolution; the combination of the medium hypotheses the base or medium scenario; and the high hypotheses the scenario of greater demographic dynamism.

1. MORTALITY

The hypotheses for the very long-term evolution of longevity were formulated for Spain as a whole and the hypotheses corresponding to each of the Autonomous Communities were subsequently derived using relational methods.

1.1. MORTALITY PROJECTION FOR SPAIN.

The national hypotheses have been constructed in two stages: in the first stage, the general level of mortality, measured in terms of life expectancy at birth (e_0), has been projected, and in the second stage, the corresponding mortality tables have been derived using standard tables.

1) Projection of the general level of mortality by fitting a logistic function with two asymptotes. The parameters of the function were estimated from the observed evolution of life expectancy at birth by sex between 1991 and 2019. The values for the years 2020 and 2021 have not been considered as they are influenced by mortality due to Covid-19.

First, the logistic transformation of the observed series of e_0 is performed by:

$$\text{Logit}(e_0^t) = \ln \left(\frac{e_0^{\max} - e_0^t}{e_0^t - e_0^{\min}} \right)$$

with t being the year (1991, 1992...2019), e_0^t the observed life expectancy at birth, e_0^{\min} the value of the lower asymptote and e_0^{\max} the value of the upper asymptote.

The lower asymptote of life expectancy is set at 30 years for both sexes, while the upper asymptote is set to achieve certain life expectancy targets by the year 2099. In the low hypothesis it is considered that life expectancy for men will reach 86 years at the end of this century and for women 91 years. In the medium scenario, life expectancy in 2099 is set at 90 years for men and 94 years for women, while in the high scenario these values reach 94 and 97 years, respectively. In comparative terms, and for the end of this century, the United Nations projections estimate in their average variant a life expectancy for Spanish men of 91 years and almost 96 years for women. For its part, the Statistical Office of Europe places these values in its high scenario at 93 years for men and 97 years for women.

Subsequently, the regression line $\alpha + \beta t$ of the logit values as a function of time is calculated and the fitted logits are obtained from the parameters of the line:

$$\text{Logit}^{ajuste}(e_0^t) = \alpha + \beta t$$

where t is the year (1991, 1992...2099).

From the values of the adjusted logits we obtain the life expectancy at birth for the observed and projected years up to the projection horizon (Graph 1).

$$e_0^t = e_0^{\min} + \left(\frac{e_0^{\max} - e_0^{\min}}{1 + \exp^{-\text{Logit}^{ajuste}(e_0^t)}} \right)$$

where t is the year (1991, 1992...2099).

Graph 1: Evolution and projection of life expectancy at birth. Spain. 1991-2099.

Source: 1991-2001 (INE), 2022-2099 (CED).

2) Projection of the mortality pattern and mortality tables. The mortality tables for each year of the projection are obtained from the last observed mortality pattern and a standard mortality pattern or model. By interpolation between the mortality ratios of both patterns, a set of mortality tables is generated and those that offer a life expectancy at birth similar to that previously projected by the logistic function are selected. The steps are as follows:

- a) Construction and adjustment of the baseline mortality table. Based on the data for the three-year period 2017-2019, the complete mortality table is constructed up to the exact age 100 for each sex. The mortality pattern shows fluctuations, especially before the age of 40 years due to the low number of deaths occurring at those ages. For this reason, we proceed to adjust the observed mortality ratios using a parametric function (Heligman-

Pollard, 1980), in order to smooth the mortality curve and derive the mortality force. The function is:

$$q_x^t = A^{(x+B)^C} + D \exp^{-E(\ln x - \ln F)^2} + \frac{GH^{x^k}}{1 + GH^{x^k}}$$

Parameters A, B and C reflect mortality in infancy. Parameter A is similar to the risk of dying in the second year of life (q1); parameter B measures differentials in the risks of dying in the first years of life; and parameter C measures the rate of decline of mortality in childhood.

Parameters D, E and F measure the presence of an overmortality trend in young-adult ages: F indicates the age of maximum overmortality, D its intensity and E its duration.

The parameters G, H and K express the mortality linked to the aging process: G the level, H the growth rate with age and K adjusts the curve at advanced ages.

b) Choice standard table. The reference tables used correspond to the West family of the United Nations standard tables, using level 96 for men and 98 for women.

c) Obtaining the projected mortality tables. From the adjusted mortality table for the five-year period 2017-19 and the selected model table, a comprehensive set of mortality tables is generated by linear interpolation between the mortality ratios of the adjusted and model tables. Figure 2 presents the observed and adjusted mortality ratios for 2017-2019, and the projected ratios in accordance with the life expectancy at birth assumptions formulated for the year 2099. Finally, those mortality tables are selected that offer levels of life expectancy at birth closest to those projected by the logistic function.

Figure 2: Observed (2017-2019) and projected (2099) sex and age-specific mortality ratios. Spain.

Source: 1991-2001 (INE), 2022-2099 (CED).

3) Finally, from the projected mortality tables, the mortality input for the projection of Spain is obtained:

$$m_{s,x}^{t,Sc;ESP}$$

where t is the year (2022, 2023...2099), Sc is the mortality hypothesis (low, medium, high) and ESP Spain.

1.2. MORTALITY PROJECTION OF THE AUTONOMOUS COMMUNITIES.

The mortality projection for the Autonomous Communities has been made by means of a relational approach that integrates, on the one hand, the expected evolution of mortality levels in Spain and, on the other, the differentials between the Autonomous Communities and Spain as a whole. The method used was the Brass logit method, which synthesizes the relationship established between two mortality tables in two parameters. The initial parameters were estimated from the logit transformation of the survival function of the mortality tables for the three-year period 2017-19 of the ACs and Spain:

$$\log i t(l_{s,x}^{2017-2019}) = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{l_{s,0}^{2017-2019} - l_{s,x}^{2017-2019}}{l_{s,x}^{2017-19}} \right)$$

$$\log i t(l_{s,x}^{ACs,2017-2019}) = \alpha_s^{ACs,2017-2019} + \beta_s^{ACs,2017-2019} * \log i t(l_{s,x}^{ESP,2017-2019})$$

where: x is age, s is sex and l is the survival function of the mortality table.

For each Autonomous Community and sex, the alpha and beta parameters of the straight line for the three-year period 2017-19 were obtained (Table 1). A negative alpha value indicates that the overall level of mortality is more favourable than in Spain, while a positive value expresses a higher level of mortality. For its part, a beta value below unity reflects that the relative structure of the mortality force is better at older ages, while a higher value indicates the opposite situation.

The key question lies in establishing the future values of the alpha and beta parameters for each year of the projected period. In other words, whether there will be a convergence in the levels and structure of mortality between the Autonomous Communities and Spain, and what its intensity will be. For all the hypotheses it has been considered that the differences in mortality will be gradually reduced until they are halved by the end of the century. The values of the alpha and beta parameters for each year of the projection have been obtained by linear interpolation between those observed in the three-year period 2017-2019 and those established in 2099.

Table 1: Alpha and beta parameters of the logit model. Autonomous Communities. 2017-2019.

	Men		Women	
	alfa	beta	alfa	beta
01 Andalucía	0,093	1,022	0,119	1,033
02 Aragón	-0,011	1,007	-0,038	0,995
03 Asturias, Principado de	0,074	1,027	0,052	1,040
04 Balears, Illes	-0,018	0,990	0,006	0,989
05 Canarias	0,018	0,985	0,078	1,001
06 Cantabria	0,033	1,087	-0,040	0,970
07 Castilla y León	-0,069	0,974	-0,073	0,981
08 Castilla - La Mancha	-0,025	1,006	-0,012	0,999
09 Cataluña	-0,017	1,003	-0,027	1,004
10 Comunitat Valenciana	0,033	1,016	0,058	1,030
11 Extremadura	0,048	0,989	0,055	1,029
12 Galicia	0,024	1,006	-0,012	0,988
13 Madrid, Comunidad de	-0,125	0,969	-0,110	0,980
14 Murcia, Región de	0,040	1,012	0,059	0,998
15 Navarra, C. F. de	-0,065	0,998	-0,086	0,985
16 País Vasco	-0,012	1,003	-0,059	0,976
17 Rioja, La	-0,035	1,000	-0,082	0,955
18 Ceuta	0,092	0,888	0,197	1,010
19 Melilla	0,006	0,857	0,095	0,878

Source: CED.

Once the value of the parameters for each year of the projection, sex and Autonomous Community had been set, the survival function of their mortality tables was obtained from those previously projected for Spain by means of:

$$\text{Logit} (l_{s,x}^{ACs,t}) = \alpha_s^{ACs,t} + \beta_s^{ACs,t} \times \text{Logit} (l_{s,x}^{C.ESP,t})$$

$$l_{s,x}^{ACs,t} = \frac{l_0}{1 + e^{2 \times \text{Logit}(l_{s,x}^{ESP,t})}}$$

where t is the year (2022,2023...2099), x is age, s is sex and l is the survival function of the mortality table.

Finally, we proceed to construct the corresponding mortality tables for the Autonomous Communities based on the projected survival functions. Table 2 shows the projected life expectancies in 2050 and 2099 by sex and Autonomous Community for each mortality evolution hypothesis.

Table 2: Life expectancy at birth by sex according to different hypotheses of national evolution of mortality. Autonomous Communities. 2050 and 2099.

		Low scenario		Medium scenario		High scenario	
		2050	2099	2050	2099	2050	2099
Men	01 Andalucía	84,10	85,86	85,76	89,83	87,02	93,74
	02 Aragón	84,81	86,55	86,45	90,46	87,69	94,28
	03 Asturias, Principado de	84,25	86,01	85,91	89,97	87,16	93,86
	04 Balears, Illes	84,82	86,56	86,46	90,47	87,71	94,29
	05 Canarias	84,55	86,30	86,20	90,23	87,45	94,08
	06 Cantabria	84,68	86,42	86,32	90,36	87,57	94,21
	07 Castilla y León	85,15	86,89	86,79	90,77	88,02	94,54
	08 Castilla - La Mancha	84,90	86,64	86,54	90,55	87,79	94,36
	09 Cataluña	84,85	86,59	86,48	90,50	87,73	94,31
	10 Comunitat Valenciana	84,52	86,27	86,16	90,21	87,42	94,06
	11 Extremadura	84,34	86,09	85,99	90,04	87,24	93,92
	12 Galicia	84,55	86,30	86,20	90,24	87,45	94,09
	13 Madrid, Comunidad de	85,54	87,27	87,17	91,12	88,40	94,84
	14 Murcia, Región de	84,46	86,21	86,11	90,15	87,36	94,02
	15 Navarra, C.F. de	85,17	86,91	86,81	90,79	88,04	94,57
	16 País Vasco	84,80	86,55	86,44	90,46	87,69	94,28
	17 Rioja, La	84,96	86,70	86,60	90,60	87,84	94,40
	18 Ceuta	83,73	85,52	85,39	89,50	86,65	93,43
	19 Melilla	83,80	85,55	85,45	89,48	86,70	93,33
Women	01 Andalucía	88,88	90,79	89,95	93,67	90,78	96,41
	02 Aragón	89,75	91,63	90,80	94,45	91,62	97,10
	03 Asturias, Principado de	89,31	91,20	90,37	94,06	91,19	96,76
	04 Balears, Illes	89,47	91,36	90,53	94,19	91,35	96,87
	05 Canarias	89,05	90,96	90,12	93,82	90,94	96,54
	06 Cantabria	89,71	91,59	90,76	94,40	91,57	97,05
	07 Castilla y León	89,93	91,80	90,98	94,61	91,79	97,24
	08 Castilla - La Mancha	89,60	91,49	90,66	94,31	91,47	96,98
	09 Cataluña	89,70	91,58	90,76	94,40	91,57	97,06
	10 Comunitat Valenciana	89,25	91,14	90,31	94,00	91,13	96,70
	11 Extremadura	89,27	91,16	90,33	94,02	91,15	96,72
	12 Galicia	89,58	91,46	90,64	94,29	91,45	96,96
	13 Madrid, Comunidad de	90,15	92,02	91,20	94,81	92,01	97,41
	14 Murcia, Región de	89,17	91,06	90,23	93,92	91,05	96,63
	15 Navarra, C.F. de	90,02	91,89	91,07	94,69	91,88	97,31
	16 País Vasco	89,84	91,71	90,89	94,52	91,70	97,16
	17 Rioja, La	89,93	91,80	90,98	94,60	91,79	97,22
	18 Ceuta	88,33	90,59	89,41	93,47	90,24	96,20
	19 Melilla	88,09	90,01	89,16	92,89	89,99	95,63

Source: CED.

The mortality input for the projection of the Autonomous Communities is obtained from the projected mortality tables:

$$m_{s,x}^{t,Sc;ACs}$$

where t is the year (2022, 2023...2099), Sc is the mortality hypothesis (low, medium, high) and ACs is the Autonomous Community.

2. FERTILITY

The hypotheses for the very long-term evolution of fertility have been formulated for Spain as a whole and the hypotheses corresponding to each of the Autonomous Communities have subsequently been derived using relational methods.

2.1. FERTILITY PROJECTION FOR SPAIN.

The national hypotheses have been constructed by establishing three levels of fertility in the very long term (Graph 3). The low hypothesis assumes that at the end of this century the fertility of Spanish women will stand at 1.10 children, i.e., a context of very low and late fertility will be maintained. The medium hypothesis considers a recovery of fertility in the short term and its subsequent stabilization at values of around 1.50 children per woman. Finally, the high scenario estimates a more intense fertility recovery in the short term to reach 1.90 children per woman in 2099. These values are similar to those predicted by the United Nations, with a fertility level for Spain of 1.05 children in the low scenario, 1.54 children in the medium scenario and 2.04 in the high scenario. For its part, Eurostat estimates fertility levels for Spanish women of 1.6 children in its base scenario and 1.29 in the low scenario for the end of the century.

Graph 3: Evolution and projection of the total fertility rate. Spain. 1980-2099.

Source: 1991-2001 (INE), 2022-2099 (CED).

In relation to the fertility pattern by age, a simplification has been made by considering that it will remain constant and will be identical for the three hypotheses of future fertility evolution. The relative pattern has been calculated with data for the five-year period 2017-2021 and smoothed by a three-age moving average (Graph 4)

Graph 4: Relative fertility pattern. Spain 2017-2021.

Source: CED

From the average number of children per woman (TFR) and the relative fertility structure of 2017-2021 ($\%f_x$), fertility rates by simple maternal age were obtained for each fertility scenario and year of the projected period:

$$f_x^{t,Sc;ESP} = TFR^{t,Sc;ESP} * \%f_x^{2017-2021;ESP} *$$

where t is the year (2022, 2023...2099), x is the age, Sc is the fertility hypothesis (low, medium, high) and ESP Spain.

2.2. FERTILITY PROJECTION OF THE AUTONOMOUS COMMUNITIES.

The hypotheses for the Autonomous Communities have been made with a similar approximation to those for Spain as a whole. First, the average number of children per woman in each Autonomous Community was projected and then the fertility rates by age of the mother were obtained by applying a relative fertility pattern specific to each Autonomous Community.

The average number of children per woman has been projected based on the expected evolution for Spain as a whole and considering the existence of territorial fertility differentials. These differentials have been calculated with data for the period 2017-2021 by comparing the general fertility rate of each Autonomous Region with that of Spain. For example, the fertility of Murcia is 18% higher than that of Spain and that of Andalusia by 5%, while that of Asturias is 21% lower and that of Galicia by 16%. It has been assumed that the differentials will be progressively reduced to half in the middle of this century, and will remain constant thereafter. Applying the estimated differentials for each year to the general fertility rate projected for Spain gives the corresponding general fertility rates for the Autonomous Communities for each hypothesis of future fertility evolution (Table 3).

$$difTFR^{2017-2021,ACs} = \frac{TFR^{2017-2021,ACs}}{TFR^{2017-2021,ESP}}$$

$$TFR^{t,Sc,ACs} = TFR^{t,Sc,ESP} * difTFR^{t,ACs}$$

where t is the year (2022, 2023...2099), Sc is the fertility hypothesis (low, medium, high), ACs is the Autonomous Community and ESP is Spain.

Table 3: Projection of total fertility rate. Autonomous Communities. 2050 y 2099.

	Scenario low		Scenario medium		Scenario high	
	2050	2099	2050	2099	2050	2099
01 Andalucía	1,16	1,13	1,43	1,54	1,70	1,94
02 Aragón	1,14	1,11	1,41	1,51	1,67	1,91
03 Asturias, Principado de	1,02	0,99	1,25	1,34	1,48	1,70
04 Balears, Illes	1,10	1,07	1,35	1,45	1,61	1,84
05 Canarias	1,01	0,98	1,24	1,33	1,47	1,69
06 Cantabria	1,07	1,04	1,31	1,41	1,56	1,79
07 Castilla y León	1,08	1,04	1,32	1,42	1,57	1,80
08 Castilla - La Mancha	1,14	1,10	1,40	1,51	1,66	1,91
09 Cataluña	1,17	1,13	1,43	1,54	1,70	1,95
10 Comunitat Valenciana	1,14	1,10	1,40	1,50	1,66	1,90
11 Extremadura	1,12	1,09	1,38	1,48	1,64	1,88
12 Galicia	1,04	1,01	1,28	1,38	1,52	1,75
13 Madrid, Comunidad de	1,14	1,10	1,40	1,50	1,66	1,90
14 Murcia, Región de	1,25	1,21	1,54	1,65	1,83	2,09
15 Navarra, C.F. de	1,20	1,16	1,48	1,59	1,75	2,01
16 País Vasco	1,16	1,12	1,42	1,53	1,68	1,93
17 Rioja, La	1,15	1,12	1,42	1,52	1,68	1,93
18 Ceuta	1,31	1,27	1,62	1,74	1,92	2,20
19 Melilla	1,58	1,53	1,94	2,09	2,31	2,65

Source: CED.

As for Spain, the relative fertility patterns of the different Autonomous Communities for the period 2017-2021 have been calculated and smoothed. These patterns have been held constant over time and are identical for the three fertility scenarios. The specific fertility rates by maternal age for each ACs have been obtained by multiplying the one-year general fertility rate by the corresponding relative fertility pattern.

$$f_x^{t,Sc,ACs} = TFR^{t,Sc,ACs} * \%f_x^{2017-2021,ACs} *$$

where t is the year (2022, 2023...2099), x is the age, Sc is the fertility hypothesis (low, medium, high) and ACs is the Autonomous Community.

3. FOREIGN MIGRATION

Foreign migration is the demographic phenomenon that presents the greatest uncertainty in relation to its future evolution. In the first two decades of the century as a whole, the foreign migratory balance has contributed around 5.8 million people to the growth of the Spanish population, but this balance has been characterized by strong fluctuations depending on the economic situation.

3.1. PROJECTION OF SPAIN'S FOREIGN MIGRATION.

In the projection of foreign migration, three hypotheses have been formulated for the evolution of immigration and emigration, contrasting their results in terms of the resulting migratory balance. In both flows, a moderation of their volumes is foreseen in the short term until reaching base levels at the end of the present decade, which will subsequently remain constant. In the case of immigration, the base flows are estimated at 400 thousand immigrants per year in the low hypothesis, 500 thousand in the medium hypothesis and 600 thousand in the high hypothesis, while in the case of emigration these values are estimated at 300 thousand, 250 thousand and 200 thousand people, respectively (Graph 5). For the 2022-2099 period as a whole, the average annual migratory balance is 108,000 persons in the low hypothesis, 256,000 in the medium hypothesis and 403,000 in the high hypothesis, In comparative terms, the INE projection base 2022 estimates for the 2022-1971 period a foreign balance that on average is equivalent to some 294,000 persons/year. For the period 2022-2099 as a whole, the Eurostat projection base 2019 establishes three migration balance hypotheses that in average terms represent 117,000 persons/year for the low, 175,000 for the medium and 232,000 for the high.

Figure 5: Projected outward migration flows. Spain 2022-2030.

Note: flows after the year 2030 remain constant at the values forecast for that year, for this reason they have not been plotted.

Source: CED

The total number of entries to Spain for each year of the population has been distributed by sex and age. The distribution by sex has been made based on the sex ratio of foreign migration observed in the period 2015-2019, and the distribution by age based on the relative migration patterns of each sex in the same period (Figure 6). Both components of out-migration have remained constant throughout the projection period.

$$i_{x,m}^{t,Sc;ESP} = I^{t,Sc;ESP} * \frac{I_m^{2015-2019,ESP}}{I^{2015-2019,ESP}} * \%i_{x,m}^{2015-2019,ESP}$$

$$i_{x,w}^{t,Sc;ESP} = I^{t,Sc;ESP} * \left(1 - \frac{I_m^{2015-2019,ESP}}{I^{2015-2019,ESP}}\right) * \%i_{x,w}^{2015-2019,ESP}$$

where t is the year (2022, 2023...2099), Sc is the immigration hypothesis (low, medium, high), x is age, m is men, w is women and ESP is Spain.

Figure 6: Relative patterns of immigration and emigration by sex. Spain 2015-2019.

Source: CED

Emigration depends on the propensity to emigrate of the resident population in Spain and its size and age structure. Therefore, unlike immigration, which is treated as absolute values, in the projection models the input consists of emigration rates by sex and age. The general hypothesis is formulated in terms of total emigrants and for this reason a series of procedures are carried out in order to obtain emigration rates in accordance with these total flows. The procedure consists of different stages:

- a) The projected total number of emigrants is distributed between men and women based on the male to female ratio of out-migration for the period 2015-2019. This ratio remains constant throughout the projected period.
- b) From the out-migration rates by sex and simple age for the period 2015-2019, the relative patterns of out-migration by age for males and females are calculated. These patterns are held constant over the entire projection period.
- c) Using the basic projection formulas and by means of an iterative procedure, age-specific emigration rates are calculated for each sex and year of the projection, from which a total number of emigrants by sex is derived in accordance with the projected number of emigrants.

The final input of out-migration in the projection model is, therefore, emigration rates by sex and age.

$$e_{x,s}^{t,Sc;ESP}$$

where t is the year (2022, 2023...2099), Sc is the emigration hypothesis (low, medium, high), x is age, s is sex and ESP is Spain.

3.2. PROJECTION OF FOREIGN MIGRATION OF THE AUTONOMOUS COMMUNITIES.

The flow of immigration from abroad to Spain has been assigned to the different Autonomous Communities by means of territorial distribution matrices calculated from data for the 2015-2016 period. The attractiveness of the regions varies according to the sex and age of the immigrants, and for this reason the specific distribution has been considered according to these variables.

$$i_{x,s}^{t,Sc,ACs} = i_{x,s}^{t,Sc,ESP} * M_{x,s}^{2015-2019,ACs}$$

where t is the year (2022, 2023... 2099), Sc is the immigration hypothesis, x is age, s is sex, M is the distribution matrix, ACs is the Autonomous Community and ESP is Spain.

Table 4: Distribution of foreign immigration to Spain according to the Autonomous Community of destination. 2015-2019.

	Men	Women	Total
01 Andalucía	12,4%	11,6%	12,0%
02 Aragón	2,3%	2,3%	2,3%
03 Asturias, Principado de	0,9%	1,1%	1,0%
04 Balears, Illes	3,5%	3,6%	3,5%
05 Canarias	6,1%	6,5%	6,3%
06 Cantabria	0,6%	0,7%	0,7%
07 Castilla y León	2,3%	2,5%	2,4%
08 Castilla - La Mancha	2,7%	2,7%	2,7%
09 Cataluña	24,6%	22,9%	23,8%
10 Comunitat Valenciana	13,1%	12,7%	12,9%
11 Extremadura	0,6%	0,6%	0,6%
12 Galicia	2,9%	3,1%	3,0%
13 Madrid, Comunidad de	18,7%	21,4%	20,0%
14 Murcia, Región de	3,4%	2,7%	3,1%
15 Navarra, C.F. de	1,3%	1,3%	1,3%
16 País Vasco	3,6%	3,6%	3,6%
17 Rioja, La	0,5%	0,5%	0,5%
18 Ceuta	0,1%	0,1%	0,1%
19 Melilla	0,2%	0,2%	0,2%
Total	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Note: as an example, the matrix for total immigration is presented, although specific matrices for each age and sex have been used in the model.

Source: CED

For emigration abroad, emigration rates by sex and simple age have been projected for each of the Autonomous Communities under the condition that the sum of emigrants abroad from all the Autonomous Communities was identical to the foreign emigration flow forecast in each of the scenarios for Spain as a whole. The procedure consists of different stages:

- a) Calculation of the differential in emigration intensity between the Autonomous Communities and Spain. With the data for the period 2015-2019, the emigration rates by sex and simple age of all the Autonomous Communities and Spain have been calculated. From the sum of these rates for each sex, a Synthetic Index of Foreign Migration (ISMext) by sex is obtained, which summarizes the intensity of emigration abroad of residents in

each Autonomous Community, subsequently calculating the corresponding differential with Spain (Table 5).

Table 5: ISMext by sex of the Autonomous Communities and differential with Spain. 2015-2019.

	ISMext		Diferencial	
	Men	Women	Men	Women
01 Andalucía	0,62	0,48	0,81	0,74
02 Aragón	0,63	0,51	0,82	0,78
03 Asturias, Principado de	0,40	0,39	0,53	0,61
04 Balears, Illes	0,74	0,65	0,97	1,00
05 Canarias	0,97	0,81	1,27	1,24
06 Cantabria	0,43	0,37	0,56	0,57
07 Castilla y León	0,41	0,38	0,53	0,59
08 Castilla - La Mancha	0,49	0,42	0,65	0,65
09 Cataluña	1,01	0,86	1,33	1,32
10 Comunitat Valenciana	1,27	1,02	1,67	1,57
11 Extremadura	0,23	0,20	0,30	0,30
12 Galicia	0,37	0,33	0,49	0,51
13 Madrid, Comunidad de	0,92	0,87	1,21	1,34
14 Murcia, Región de	0,92	0,66	1,21	1,01
15 Navarra, C.F. de	0,60	0,52	0,79	0,80
16 País Vasco	0,53	0,44	0,70	0,68
17 Rioja, La	0,61	0,54	0,80	0,82
18 Ceuta	0,61	0,43	0,80	0,66
19 Melilla	1,10	0,67	1,45	1,02
España	0,76	0,65		

Source: CED

$$difISMext_s^{2015-2019,ACs} = \frac{ISMext_s^{2015-2019,ACs}}{ISM_s^{2015-2019,ESP}}$$

where s is the sex, ACs is the Autonomous Community and ESP is Spain.

- b) Calculation of the ISMext by sex for each Autonomous Community, projection year and out-migration scenario. It is assumed that the differential observed in 2015-2019 is reduced linearly to half in the middle of this century and then remains constant. Applying the differential for each year to the ISMext projected for Spain as a whole gives the corresponding ISMext for each Autonomous Community and foreign emigration scenario.

$$ISMext_s^{t,Sc,ESP} = \sum_0^{100} e_s^{t,Sc,ESP}$$

$$ISMext_s^{t,Sc,CCAA} = ISMext_s^{t,Sc,ESP} * difISMext_s^{t,CCAA}$$

where t (2022, 2023... 2099), s is sex, x is age, e is the foreign emigration rate, $CCAA$ is the Autonomous Community and ESP is Spain.

- c) Calculation of out-migration rates by sex and age by sex for each Autonomous Community, projection year and out-migration scenario. The ISMext are disaggregated by simple age using a relative pattern of emigration by sex specific to each of the Autonomous Communities. These patterns are calculated with data for the period 2015-2019 and are held constant over time (Graph 6).

$$e_{s,x}^{t,Sc,ACs} = ISMext_s^{t,Sc,ACs} * \%e_{s,x}^{2015-2019,ACs}$$

where t (2022, 2023... 2099), s is sex, x is age, %e is the relative pattern of emigration abroad and ACs is the Autonomous Community.

Graph 6: Some examples of relative patterns of emigration abroad. Autonomous Communities. 2015-2019.

Source: CED

The rates of emigration abroad by sex and age constitute the external migration input of the projection model of the Autonomous Communities.

$$e_{s,x}^{t,Sc,ACs}$$

where t (2022, 2023... 2099), s is sex, x is age and ACs is the Autonomous Community.

4. INTERNAL MIGRATION

In the projection of the Autonomous Communities, in addition to mortality, fertility and foreign migration, internal migratory exchanges between these regions must be considered. Migratory flows between Autonomous Communities have been projected by applying to the resident population in each of them the corresponding projected rates of internal emigration according to sex, age and Autonomous Community of destination for each of the years of the projected period. In this way, the internal outflows from each Autonomous Community are obtained and the corresponding inflows are subsequently derived from the sum of the internal emigrants from the rest of the Autonomous Communities to that region.

The matrix of internal emigration rates has been calculated using a multiplicative model that has three elements: an indicator of the future intensity of internal migration, a calendar of its relative pattern by age and an origin-destination matrix that synthesizes the spatial distribution model of internal migration in Spain. From these three elements, internal migration rates are calculated as follows:

$$eint_{x,s,i,j} = ISM int_{s,i} \times C_{x,s,i} \times M_{x,s,i,j}$$

where x is age, s is sex, i is the region of origin, j is the region of destination, $ISMint$ is the synthetic index of internal migration, C is the relative timing of this migration, and M is the origin-destination matrix.

The parameters of the multiplicative model for the projection of rates have been calculated with the data for the three-year period 2017-2019 as follows:

- Migratory intensity. The propensity to emigrate from one Autonomous Community to the rest of the Autonomous Communities has been synthesized in a Synthetic Index of Internal Migration (ISMint) by sex. This index is the sum of the age-specific rates of internal emigration

$$ISMint_s^{2017-2019,ACs} = \sum_0^{95} eint_{s,x}^{2017-2019,ACs}$$

where x is age, s is sex, $eint$ is the internal migration rate and ACs is the Autonomous Community.

The ISMint for the 2017-2019 period has remained constant throughout the entire projection period (Table 6).

Table 6: Synthetic Index of Internal Migration. Autonomous Communities. 2017-2019

	Men	Women
01 Andalucía	0,692	0,650
02 Aragón	1,137	1,035
03 Asturias, Principado de	0,931	0,940
04 Balears, Illes	1,506	1,377
05 Canarias	0,924	0,854
06 Cantabria	1,195	1,192
07 Castilla y León	1,269	1,307
08 Castilla - La Mancha	1,820	1,854
09 Cataluña	0,604	0,569
10 Comunitat Valenciana	0,834	0,800
11 Extremadura	1,173	1,184
12 Galicia	0,676	0,662
13 Madrid, Comunidad de	1,130	1,088
14 Murcia, Región de	1,053	0,937
15 Navarra, C.F. de	1,013	1,037
16 País Vasco	0,762	0,737
17 Rioja, La	1,359	1,383
18 Ceuta	2,815	2,314
19 Melilla	3,429	2,719

Source: CED.

- Internal migration calendar. The migration calendars for each sex and Autonomous Community have been calculated from the specific rates of internal emigration by simple age. The resulting relative patterns have been smoothed by means of a double moving average that considers the three preceding and following ages (Graph 7). These smoothed patterns have been held constant throughout the projection period.
- The matrix of internal exchanges has been calculated by simple age and sex, and has been kept constant. This matrix indicates the relative distribution of outflows from an Autonomous Community to the rest of the Autonomous Communities.

Graph 7: Some examples of relative patterns of internal emigration. Autonomous Communities. 2017-2019.

Source: CED.

Finally, the multiplicative model is used to obtain the internal migration input for the projection of the Autonomous Communities:

$$eint_{s,x}^{t,ACsOri,ACsDest}$$

where t is the year (2022, 2023...2099), s is the sex, x is the simple age, ACsOri is the Autonomous Community of origin and ACsDest is the destination Autonomous Community.

RESULTS

Below are some graphs and tables that summarize the main results of the demographic scenarios of the multiregional population projection model for Spain and its Autonomous Communities.

Evolution and projection of Spain's population according to different scenarios. 2000-2100.

Source: CED.

Evolution and projection of the components of Spain's population growth according to different scenarios. 2000-2099.

Source: CED.

Population pyramids of Spain observed in 2022 and projected to 2050 and 2100 according to different scenarios.

Source: CED.

Total population observed in 2022 and projected to 2050 and 2100 for the Autonomous Communities according to different scenarios.

Escenario	Población en miles			Cambio absoluto en miles			Cambio relativo en porcentaje			Peso relativo en España		
	2022	2050	2099	2022-2050	2050-2099	2022-2099	2022-2050	2050-2099	2022-2099	2022	2050	2099
medium												
Andalucía	8.500	8.920	8.146	420	-775	-355	5%	-9%	-4%	17,9%	17,2%	15,7%
Aragón	1.326	1.383	1.373	57	-11	46	4%	-1%	3%	2,8%	2,7%	2,6%
Asturias	1.005	849	634	-156	-215	-371	-16%	-25%	-37%	2,1%	1,6%	1,2%
Baleares, Illes	1.177	1.513	1.736	336	223	560	29%	15%	48%	2,5%	2,9%	3,3%
Canarias	2.178	2.590	2.738	412	148	560	19%	6%	26%	4,6%	5,0%	5,3%
Cantabria	585	550	454	-36	-96	-132	-6%	-17%	-23%	1,2%	1,1%	0,9%
Castilla y León	2.373	2.111	1.689	-262	-422	-684	-11%	-20%	-29%	5,0%	4,1%	3,2%
Castilla - La Mancha	2.053	2.102	1.901	49	-201	-152	2%	-10%	-7%	4,3%	4,1%	3,7%
Cataluña	7.793	9.357	10.535	1.564	1.179	2.743	20%	13%	35%	16,4%	18,1%	20,3%
Comunitat Valenciana	5.098	5.527	5.604	429	77	506	8%	1%	10%	10,7%	10,7%	10,8%
Extremadura	1.055	969	722	-86	-246	-332	-8%	-25%	-32%	2,2%	1,9%	1,4%
Galicia	2.690	2.424	1.940	-266	-484	-750	-10%	-20%	-28%	5,7%	4,7%	3,7%
Madrid	6.750	8.193	9.130	1.443	937	2.380	21%	11%	35%	14,2%	15,8%	17,5%
Murcia	1.532	1.752	1.822	220	70	290	14%	4%	19%	3,2%	3,4%	3,5%
Navarra	664	748	797	84	49	133	13%	7%	20%	1,4%	1,4%	1,5%
País Vasco	2.208	2.276	2.246	68	-30	37	3%	-1%	2%	4,7%	4,4%	4,3%
Rioja, La	320	329	313	9	-16	-7	3%	-5%	-2%	0,7%	0,6%	0,6%
Ceuta	83	96	96	13	0	13	16%	0%	16%	0,2%	0,2%	0,2%
Melilla	85	116	149	31	33	64	36%	28%	75%	0,2%	0,2%	0,3%
ESPAÑA	47.475	51.805	52.025	4.329	220	4.549	9%	0%	10%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%
low												
Andalucía	8.500	8.077	5.371	-423	-2.706	-3.129	-5%	-33%	-37%	17,9%	17,7%	16,6%
Aragón	1.326	1.232	873	-94	-359	-453	-7%	-29%	-34%	2,8%	2,7%	2,7%
Asturias	1.005	776	424	-228	-352	-581	-23%	-45%	-58%	2,1%	1,7%	1,3%
Baleares, Illes	1.177	1.325	1.102	148	-223	-74	13%	-17%	-6%	2,5%	2,9%	3,4%
Canarias	2.178	2.266	1.737	89	-529	-440	4%	-23%	-20%	4,6%	5,0%	5,4%
Cantabria	585	501	303	-84	-198	-282	-14%	-40%	-48%	1,2%	1,1%	0,9%
Castilla y León	2.373	1.931	1.128	-442	-803	-1.245	-19%	-42%	-52%	5,0%	4,2%	3,5%
Castilla - La Mancha	2.053	1.903	1.241	-150	-662	-813	-7%	-35%	-40%	4,3%	4,2%	3,8%
Cataluña	7.793	8.007	6.207	215	-1.801	-1.586	3%	-22%	-20%	16,4%	17,5%	19,1%
Comunitat Valenciana	5.098	4.770	3.345	-328	-1.424	-1.753	-6%	-30%	-34%	10,7%	10,4%	10,3%
Extremadura	1.055	906	510	-149	-396	-544	-14%	-44%	-52%	2,2%	2,0%	1,6%
Galicia	2.690	2.222	1.321	-469	-901	-1.370	-17%	-41%	-51%	5,7%	4,9%	4,1%
Madrid	6.750	7.048	5.419	298	-1.629	-1.332	4%	-23%	-20%	14,2%	15,4%	16,7%
Murcia	1.532	1.544	1.127	12	-417	-405	1%	-27%	-26%	3,2%	3,4%	3,5%
Navarra	664	664	504	0	-159	-160	0%	-24%	-24%	1,4%	1,5%	1,6%
País Vasco	2.208	2.040	1.450	-168	-590	-758	-8%	-29%	-34%	4,7%	4,5%	4,5%
Rioja, La	320	294	200	-26	-95	-120	-8%	-32%	-38%	0,7%	0,6%	0,6%
Ceuta	83	88	64	5	-24	-19	6%	-27%	-23%	0,2%	0,2%	0,2%
Melilla	85	101	88	16	-13	3	19%	-13%	3%	0,2%	0,2%	0,3%
ESPAÑA	47.475	45.696	32.414	-1.780	-13.282	-15.062	-4%	-29%	-32%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%
high												
Andalucía	8.500	9.733	11.398	1.233	1.665	2.898	15%	17%	34%	17,9%	16,8%	15,0%
Aragón	1.326	1.532	1.973	205	441	646	15%	29%	49%	2,8%	2,6%	2,6%
Asturias	1.005	917	881	-87	-37	-124	-9%	-4%	-12%	2,1%	1,6%	1,2%
Baleares, Illes	1.177	1.700	2.494	523	794	1.317	44%	47%	112%	2,5%	2,9%	3,3%
Canarias	2.178	2.910	3.918	732	1.008	1.740	34%	35%	80%	4,6%	5,0%	5,2%
Cantabria	585	596	630	10	34	45	2%	6%	8%	1,2%	1,0%	0,8%
Castilla y León	2.373	2.282	2.350	-90	67	-23	-4%	3%	-1%	5,0%	3,9%	3,1%
Castilla - La Mancha	2.053	2.293	2.673	239	381	620	12%	17%	30%	4,3%	4,0%	3,5%
Cataluña	7.793	10.734	16.002	2.941	5.269	8.210	38%	49%	105%	16,4%	18,5%	21,1%
Comunitat Valenciana	5.098	6.283	8.371	1.185	2.088	3.273	23%	33%	64%	10,7%	10,9%	11,0%
Extremadura	1.055	1.027	967	-27	-60	-88	-3%	-6%	-8%	2,2%	1,8%	1,3%
Galicia	2.690	2.617	2.662	-73	45	-28	-3%	2%	-1%	5,7%	4,5%	3,5%
Madrid	6.750	9.363	13.800	2.613	4.437	7.050	39%	47%	104%	14,2%	16,2%	18,2%
Murcia	1.532	1.956	2.658	424	702	1.126	28%	36%	74%	3,2%	3,4%	3,5%
Navarra	664	831	1.152	167	322	488	25%	39%	74%	1,4%	1,4%	1,5%
País Vasco	2.208	2.507	3.203	299	696	995	14%	28%	45%	4,7%	4,3%	4,2%
Rioja, La	320	363	451	43	88	131	13%	24%	41%	0,7%	0,6%	0,6%
Ceuta	83	105	134	21	29	51	26%	28%	61%	0,2%	0,2%	0,2%
Melilla	85	131	226	46	95	140	54%	72%	165%	0,2%	0,2%	0,3%
ESPAÑA	47.475	57.879	75.943	10.403	18.064	28.467	22%	31%	60%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Source: CED.

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